

Synthesis, cyclic voltammetry, spectral studies and magnetic moment on copper(II) complexes with N₂S₃ and N₄ donor macrocyclic ligands

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Copper(II) complexes with general formula Cu(L)₂X₂ (where L = ligand L₁ or L₂, X = CH₃COO⁻Cl⁻, NO₃⁻ and 1/2 SO₄²⁻) have been synthesized with N₄ and N₂S₃ donor macrocyclic ligands and characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic moments, IR, electronic, ¹H NMR and EPR spectral studies. Cyclic voltammetry has revealed the existence of two reduction couples, Cu^{II} Y Cu^I and Cu^I Y Cu⁰.

The synthesis and characterization of coordination compounds with azamacrocyclic ligands has evolved a great attention during the last years¹⁻⁴. Additional information related to the spectroscopic properties of these ligands and their coordination compounds are able to generate novel stereochemical, electrochemical electronic properties along with the exploration of the biological activity⁵. In this present paper we report the synthesis and characterization of a two series of copper(II) complexes with these macrocyclic ligands viz. L₁ = 1,10-diaza-4,7,13-trithia-2,3 : 8,9-dibenzo-cyclopentadeca-11,15-dione (L₁) and 2,4,9,11-tetraphenyl-1,5,8,12-tetraazacyclotetradeca-1,4,8,11-tetraene (L₂).

Results and discussion

All the complexes have the general composition [Cu(L₁)X]₂ and [Cu(L₂)X₂] respectively (where X = Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻ and MeCOO⁻ and Ligand = L₁ and L₂). Magnetic moments values and molar conductance values in DMF are reported in Table 1.

The mass spectrum of [Cu(L₂)SO₄] complex is recorded which gives different molecular ion peaks corresponding to molecular arrangements of the complex. It also confirms the suggested molecular formula and has a good agreement with molecular weight of the complex. Representative mass

Mass spectrum for the complex [Cu(L₂)SO₄].

spectrum of the complex [Cu(L₂)SO₄] is shown below. The spectrum shows numerous peaks representing successive degradation of the molecule. The observed peak at *m/e* 657.18 (656.26 calcd.) represents the molecular ion peak of this complex with 63.19% abundance. In present studies complex show one of the strongest peaks (base peak) at (65%) *m/e* 145.09 represents the most stable species.

Electronic spectra :

[Cu(L₁)X]₂ complexes : In the electronic spectra of complexes two characteristic bands are observed at 11450–12545 cm⁻¹ and 17550–18015 cm⁻¹. These bands may be assigned to the ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g} and ²B_{1g} → ²E_g transitions respectively⁹. In the copper(II) complexes reported here the ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g} transition is shifted to higher energy, the order being Cl⁻ < NO₃⁻ < CH₃COO⁻ < SO₄²⁻.

[Cu(L₂)X₂] complexes : The electronic spectra of these complexes show one characteristic band at 10410–14511 cm⁻¹ except the acetato complex which shows two characteristic bands at 11210 and 17570 cm⁻¹, these bands may be assigned to the ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g} and ²B_{1g} → ²E_g transitions, respectively.

Table 1. Elemental analysis and magnetic moments of copper(II) complexes

Complexes	Magnetic moment	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Colour	Elemental analysis (%) : Calcd. (Found)			
						Ni	C	H	N
[Cu(L ₁)(CH ₃ COO)](CH ₃ COO) CuC ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₂ S ₃ O ₆	1.99	42.0	210	95	Green	11.11 (10.11)	46.18 (45.00)	4.20 (4.01)	4.90 (4.12)
[Cu(L ₁)Cl]Cl CuC ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₃ O ₂ Cl ₂	1.92	47.0	212	100	Green	12.10 (11.21)	41.18 (41.00)	3.46 (3.41)	5.34 (4.91)
[Cu(L ₁)(NO ₃)](NO ₃) CuC ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ S ₃ O ₈	1.98	51.0	207	105	Light green	10.99 (10.21)	37.40 (37.21)	3.14 (3.10)	9.69 (9.11)
[Cu(L ₁)SO ₄] CuC ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₄ O ₆	1.95	50.0	234	15	Dark green	11.55 (10.71)	39.30 (39.00)	3.30 (3.01)	5.09 (4.65)
[Cu(L ₂)Cl ₂] CuC ₃₄ H ₃₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	1.95	81.0	211	10	Blue	10.07 (9.89)	64.73 (64.61)	5.11 (4.92)	8.88 (8.62)
[Cu(L ₂)](NO ₃) ₂ CuC ₃₄ H ₃₂ N ₆ O ₆	1.96	85.0	221	205	Dark blue	9.29 (8.99)	59.71 (59.62)	4.68 (4.51)	12.30 (12.01)
[Cu(L ₂)(CH ₃ COO) ₂] CuC ₃₈ H ₃₈ N ₄ O ₄	1.94	75.0	222	11	Light blue	9.37 (9.15)	67.33 (67.21)	5.62 (4.35)	8.26 (8.11)
[Cu(L ₃)SO ₄] CuC ₃₄ H ₃₂ N ₄ SO ₄	1.96	65.0	224	06	Blue	9.69 (9.51)	62.25 (62.01)	4.88 (4.27)	8.54 (8.41)

[Cu(L₂)SO₄] complex : Electronic spectrum of this complex shows two electronic spectral bands at 8500 and 10600 cm⁻¹ which suggests five coordinated geometry¹⁰.

[Cu(L₂)](NO₃)₂ complex : Electronic spectrum of this complex displays three electronic spectral bands at 15603, 18854 and 31540 cm⁻¹ and has square planar geometry¹¹.

EPR spectra :

[Cu(L₁)X]X complexes : The anisotropic g-values have been calculated using the following expressions : $g_{\parallel} = 2(1 - 49/\dot{C}E_2)$ and $g_{\perp} = 2(1 - 9/\dot{C}E_3)$. Where $g = 823 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\dot{C}E_2 = {}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{1g}$, $\dot{C}E_3 = {}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$. The stronger interaction along the z axis is to be accompanied by an increase in the value of $g_{\parallel}$. The stronger axial bonding leads to an increase in the length of the bond in the XY plane, which results in a decrease of both the in-plane covalency and energy of the $d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xy}$ transition¹². Both these factors tend to increase the value of $g_{\parallel}$. The $g_{\parallel}$ values for the complexes studied follow an order $\text{SO}_4^- > \text{CH}_3\text{COO}^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{Cl}^-$ which

to a great extent is consistent with the positions of the anions in the spectrochemical series. The spectrum is consistent with a tetragonal distorted octahedral coordination of the metal ion, with the unpaired electron occupying predominantly the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital.

In addition metal-metal interaction between two copper centers can be explained by the expression $G = (g_{\parallel} - 2)/(g_{\perp} - 2)$. If the value of G is greater than four, the exchange interaction is negligible, and the value of G is less than four, a considerable interaction is indicated in solid complex. The fraction K^2 which is a measure of covalency, is calculated² and given in Table 2. The smaller the value of K^2 the more covalent is the bonding. $K^2 = 1$ indicates completely ionic bonding, while $K^2 = 0.5$ indicates complete covalent bonding¹³.

[Cu(L₂)SO₄] complex : EPR spectra of sulfato complexes with $g_3 > g_2 > g_1$, system are recorded, the ratio of $(g_2 - g_1)/(g_3 - g_2)$ called the parameter R. The value of R is

Table 2. Ligand field (cm⁻¹) parameters of copper(II) complexes

Complex	$g_{\parallel}$	$g_{\perp}$	g_{iso}	$A_{\parallel}$	$A_{\perp}$	A_{iso}	K^2	K^2
[Cu(L ₁)(CH ₃ COO)](CH ₃ COO)	2.20	2.01	2.07	166	68	101	0.71	0.71
[Cu(L ₁)Cl]Cl	2.10	2.09	2.13	170	75	107	0.99	0.99
[Cu(L ₁)(NO ₃)](NO ₃)	2.13	2.01	2.05	172	71	105	0.92	0.92
[Cu(L ₁)SO ₄]	2.27	2.06	2.13	168	74	105	0.93	0.93
[Cu(L ₂)Cl ₂]	2.17	2.04	2.08	175	70	105	0.96	0.96
[Cu(L ₂)](NO ₃) ₂	2.22	2.11	2.14	177	72	106	0.97	0.97
[Cu(L ₂)(CH ₃ COO) ₂]	2.15	1.90	1.98	171	75	107	0.92	0.92
[Cu(L ₃)SO ₄]	2.16	1.97	2.03	170	76	107	0.95 _s	0.95

quite similar as reported earlier²⁻¹⁴. The complex under study shows the value of R greater than one, thus indicating five coordinate square pyramidal geometry.

[Cu(L₂)](NO₃)₂ complex : The EPR spectrum of [Cu(L₂)](NO₃)₂ complex is recorded for crystalline samples and in DMSO solution. The g tensor values of the copper(II) complexes can be used to drive the ground state. From the observed values it is clear that $g_{||} > g_{\perp} > 2$ and the EPR parameters of the complex coincide well with reported earlier² and has square planar geometry and the systems are axially symmetric¹⁵.

Cyclic voltammetry :

Cyclic voltammetry of the complexes generally show a single electron transfer two step process in which reduction of the copper(II) complexes occurred. The electrochemical reduction for copper(II) complexes is written as follows : $Cu^{II} \rightleftharpoons Cu^I \rightleftharpoons Cu^0$. The reduction potential observed for the acetato complex comparatively less negative than the chloro, and the nitrate complexes. The electrochemical potential of the complexes of ligand (L₁) and ligand (L₂) have difference values because electrochemical potential depends upon number of donating atoms or coordination sites¹⁶.

The stability of the mixed valence species Cu^{II}/Cu^I is expressed by the conproportionation constant k_{con} for equilibrium. $Cu^{II} + Cu^I \rightleftharpoons 2[Cu^{II}Cu^I]$.

The k_{con} values of the complexes can be determined electrochemically using the following equations, $\log k_{con} = E_{1/2}/0.591$, $E_{1/2} = E_{1/2}^1 - E_{1/2}^2$, $\Delta E_p = E_{pc} - E_{pa}$ and $E_{1/2} = 0.05 (E_{pc} - E_{pa})$, E_{pc} = cathodic peak potential (-0.270 to 1.061 V), E_{pa} = anodic peak potential (-0.010 to -0.286 V). k_{con} values are calculated and it values are present in the range 8.431×10^5 to 1.35×10^2 .

Experimental

Preparation of the ligands :

(1a) Preparation of diamines. This diamine is prepared as reported earlier¹.

(1b) Preparation of ligands (L₁ and L₂). These ligands are prepared as reported earlier³.

Scheme 1. Suggested chemical reaction for the synthesis of macrocyclic ligands L₁ and L₂.

Preparation of the complexes : A hot (~75°C) aqueous ethanol solution (20.0 mL) of the metal salts (0.1 mol) and a ethanol solution (20 mL) of respective ligand (0.1 mol) were mixed in the molar ratio 1 : 1. The mixture was refluxed for about four hours at a temperature of ~80°C. On cooling the contents to a temperature of ~5°C, the complexes were separated. They were filtered, washed with 50% ethanol and dried over P₄O₁₀ in a vacuum desiccator.

Scheme 2. Probable structures of copper(II) complexes.

Physical measurements :

Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out a CAHN 2000 Faraday balance using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as the

calibrating agent. Molar conductance measurements were carried out on a Leeds Northrop Conductivity Bridge 4995. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137. The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Shimadzu UV mini-1240 spectrophotometer in DMF solution. C, H and N analysis were carried out on a Carl-Ebra 1106 elemental analyzer. Nitrogen was determined by the Kjeldahl's method. EPR spectra were recorded at room temperature on a Varion E-4 EPR spectrometer at ~9.1 GHz and 100 KHz field modulation and DPPH was used as marker. Cyclic voltammogram were measured at using an Autolab PGSTAT-12-electrochemical analyzer in MeCN solution containing tetra-n-Bu₄NClO₄ and Ag/AgCl as supporting electrode.

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